

Assessment of Knowledge, Attitude, and Practice of Pharmacoeconomics among Physicians in India: A Questionnaire-Based Survey

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ABSTRACT

Objective: Pharmacoeconomics is essential for healthcare decision-making, providing insights into the cost-effectiveness of pharmaceutical therapies. With rising healthcare costs globally, especially in developing countries like India, it becomes crucial for clinicians to understand the balance between economic efficiency and clinical efficacy. This study aims to assess the knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAP) of Indian physicians regarding Pharmacoeconomics, highlighting their awareness and integration of cost-effectiveness in clinical decisions, which is vital for improving resource allocation and patient care. **Methods:** A cross-sectional survey was conducted among 227 physicians using a structured, self-administered questionnaire. Data were collected both online and offline, covering sociodemographic details and KAP-related questions. Cronbach's alpha was used to ensure the reliability of the questionnaire, resulting in a final tool consisting of 5 knowledge, 5 attitude, and 4 practice questions. The data were analyzed using Mann-Whitney U and Kruskal-Wallis tests and Pearson correlation. **Results:** The results revealed moderate scores for knowledge, attitude, and practice (65.02%, 77.34%, and 71.08%, respectively) towards Pharmacoeconomics. Interestingly, graduate physicians scored higher in knowledge and attitude compared to postgraduates. Statistical analysis also claimed higher knowledge scores of more-experienced physicians that may be attributed to their prolonged involvement in clinical decision-making. Correlation analysis reported a significant positive association between attitude and practice scores ($r = 0.364$, $p < 0.05$). **Conclusion:** The study highlights the need for the integration of Pharmacoeconomics in healthcare curriculum and also targeted educational programs to enhance the knowledge of Pharmacoeconomics among clinicians, thereby improving its application in clinical decision-making.

Keywords: Cronbach alpha score, Kruskal-Wallis test, Mann-Whitney U test, Pearson Correlation, Physicians.

INTRODUCTION

Pharmacoeconomics is a vital component of healthcare decision-making owing to its ability to provide critical information about the relative costs of various pharmaceutical therapies. This area of study examines the relative benefits of various medications and drug therapies, weighing the direct and indirect expenses as well as how they affect patient outcomes.^[1] Pharmacoeconomics assesses these variables in order to provide well-informed guidance to stakeholders, policymakers, and healthcare professionals regarding the most efficient use of the limited resources available to them in order to maximize patient outcomes and achieve economic efficiency.^[2,3]

The importance of Pharmacoeconomics has grown significantly with the escalating costs of healthcare globally, especially in developing countries like India. Due to its limited resources and high population density, the Indian healthcare system necessitates the prudent utilization of funds to achieve the best possible health outcomes. Pharmacoeconomics evaluations help in prioritizing healthcare expenditures by evaluating the economic and clinical impacts of pharmaceutical products and therapies. The International Society of Pharmacoeconomics and Outcomes Research (ISPOR) has established an Indian chapter, dedicated to developing the pharmacoeconomics foundations of healthcare services in the region.^[4]

Despite its crucial role, the comprehension and implementation of pharmacoeconomics among healthcare professionals exhibit considerable variation. In India, the awareness and application of Pharmacoeconomics principles are still in their early stages compared to more developed Nations. This knowledge gap can result in suboptimal prescribing practices and inefficient use of healthcare resources. Research indicates that although there is increasing interest in Pharmacoeconomics among healthcare professionals, the actual incorporation of these principles into clinical practice remains limited. This limitation is due to various obstacles, including inadequate training, insufficient data, and restricted access to pharmacoeconomics resources.^[5] A recent study conducted among undergraduate medical students in India concluded that those educated on the principles of Pharmacoeconomics possess a better understanding of the costs and outcomes associated with drug therapy. Consequently, these students can contribute positively to reducing the economic burden on both patients and society.

To address these issues, it is essential to understand the current knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAP) related to Pharmacoeconomics among healthcare practitioners. This understanding can identify gaps and inform the development of targeted educational programs and policies to enhance the adoption of Pharmacoeconomics principles in clinical practice.

This present study summarizes the findings of a survey conducted to evaluate the knowledge, attitudes, and practices of Pharmacoeconomics among healthcare practitioners. By shedding light on these aspects, this study contributes to the broader goal of optimizing healthcare resource utilization and improving patient outcomes in the context of limited economic resources.

METHODS

Study Design: The present cross-sectional study was conducted by providing a structured questionnaire to the physicians both online (in the form of a Google form) and offline mode and data were collected both in e-format and in paper.

Study subjects: The questionnaire was distributed and those who were willing to participate in the study were asked to fill up the form. Initially, data was collected from 32 candidates for a pilot study. Thereafter the questionnaire was reviewed and modified as per the reliability analysis and finally, the data was collected from February 2024 to April 2024.

Data Collection Tool and Technique: For this study, a standardized, pre-tested, self-administered questionnaire was created. Five knowledge-based, five attitude-based, and five practice-based items made up the initial questionnaire. 32 people participated in a pilot study. The Cronbach's alpha test was used to assess the reliability of the questionnaire. Below are the Cronbach alpha coefficients:

	Cronbach's alpha coefficient	No. of items	Remarks
Knowledge-Based Questions	0.675	5	All items accepted
Attitude-Based Questions	0.91	5	All items accepted
Practice-Based Questions	0.46	5	Deletion of Q2 which increased the coefficient to 0.77

*Considering good reliability of questionnaire for Cronbach's alpha coefficient of ≥ 0.7 .^[6]
 The reliability test revealed that an acceptable Cronbach alpha score could be obtained by deleting 1 question from the practice section. So, the final questionnaire with their reliability score was

Sections	No. of questions	Cronbach alpha score
Knowledge	5	0.675
Attitude	5	0.91
Practice	4	0.77

The final questionnaire is composed of four sections:

Sociodemographic characteristics- 7 questions

Knowledge-related questions- 5 questions

Attitude-related questions- 5 questions

Practice-related questions- 4 questions.

Every right response to the knowledge item questions was worth one point, while any incorrect response was worth zero.

Five questions, each with a 5-point Likert scale rating, made up the answers to the attitude and practice sections. On a scale of 5 to 1, where 5 represents the most positive attitude or practice, the responses were rated. 25 was the highest attitude score. 20 was the highest possible practice score. Each response's values were computed and then examined in more detail.

The overall knowledge was classified based on Bloom's cut-off criteria:

- ✓ A score of 80-100% considered good
- ✓ 60-79% as moderate
- ✓ < 60% as poor.

Similarly, the overall attitude was categorized as follows:

- ✓ Scores of 80-100% labeled as good
- ✓ 60-79% as moderate
- ✓ Below 60% as poor.

The same cut-off criteria were applied to categorize the overall practice score.^[7]

- ✓ 80-100% considered good
- ✓ 60-79% moderate
- ✓ < 60% poor.

Data Processing and Analysis: The information was manually coded, categorized, sorted, verified, and confirmed. Numerical data is expressed as means (\pm standard error of mean), whilst categorical variables were given as numbers (percentages). KAP scores among two groups were compared using the Mann–Whitney U test, whereas comparisons between three or more groups (depending on sociodemographic factors) were compared using the Kruskal–Wallis test. SPSS was used for the statistical analysis. Any difference with a p-value below 0.05 was considered statistically significant. The Pearson correlation test was used for correlation analysis.^[8]

RESULTS

Sociodemographic Characteristics: Overall 227 doctors voluntarily participated in the survey. Out of them 83.26% (189) were males, indicating a male preponderance. The participating physicians were between the ages of 23 to 66 years, with the majority of them (65, 28.63%) falling between the ages of 44 and 47 years. Participants in the study were 43.56 ± 7.94 years old on average.

Majority of the doctors who participated in the study held a post-graduate (PG) or higher degree. Only 12.33% (28) of the study participants were undergraduates (UG). This could be correlated with the age of the subjects as there were very few participants in the lower age group. The specialization of the physicians included urologists (16.74%), followed by orthopedics (15%), pediatrics (12%), and gynecology (10.5%). The years of experience in clinical practice of the participating physicians were noted and it was found that the majority (33.48%) of the doctors had experience of 11 to 15 years.

KAP Scores: The average knowledge score (KS), attitude score (AS), and practice score (PS) are highlighted in Table 1. As per Bloom’s cut-off point, Table 1 reflects that the knowledge, attitude, and practice scores toward Pharmacoeconomics were moderate.

Table 1: Scores of the KAP study

	Total score obtained (n)/ Total score (N)	Mean score (%)	Std. deviation	General Impression
Knowledge	738/1135	3.25 (65.02)	0.88	Moderate
Attitude	4389/5675	19.33 (77.34)	1.96	Moderate
Practice	3227/4540	14.22 (71.08)	1.57	Moderate

The KAP scores were further evaluated based on the sociodemographic characteristics (Table 2). Based on the gender of the participants, the scores were computed and Mann–Whitney test confirmed that the scores were not significantly different among the males and females ($p > 0.05$). Mann–Whitney test further validated insignificant differences in knowledge score and practice score among the UG and PG participants. However, the analysis indicated a significantly lower attitude score among the PG participants compared to their UG counterparts ($p < 0.05$). Kruskal–Wallis analysis demonstrated a significant difference in both knowledge and attitude scores across participants with varying years of experience. Notably, physicians with more years of experience exhibited higher knowledge scores.

Table 2: KAP scores vs sociodemographic characteristics.

Sociodemographic characteristics		Knowledge		Attitude		Practice	
		Mean Score	p-value	Mean Score	p-value	Mean Score	p-value
Gender	Male	3.26	0.423 ^a	19.31	0.942 ^a	14.16	0.204 ^a
	Female	3.16		19.47		14.47	
Qualification	UG	3.43	0.111 ^a	20.32	0.026^a	14.39	0.337 ^a
	PG	3.23		19.20		14.19	
Years of experience	0-4	2.87	0.022^b	21.07	0.010^b	14.47	0.587 ^b
	5-10	3.23		18.75		14.11	
	11-15	3.36		19.55		14.12	
	16-20	3.28		19.37		14.00	
	21-25	3.35		19.06		14.52	
	26-30	3.20		18.00		14.50	
	31-35	2.29		19.57		14.57	
	36-40	5.00		21.00		17.00	

Bold and italics values indicate statistical significance ($p < 0.05$). ^aMann–Whitney test; ^bKruskal–Wallis test.

Scores were further analyzed based on the participants' specialization (Figure 1). Practice and attitude scores were significantly higher among respondents from the Endocrinology department, while the Pharmacology department showed higher attitude scores.

Figure 1: Score of the participants based on their specialization.

Correlation between knowledge, attitude, and practice scores has been summarized in Figure 2. Pearson correlation analysis revealed weak positive correlation among KS and AS ($r= 0.035$, $p= 0.595$) and KS and PS ($r= 0.005$, $p= 0.935$). However, highly significant positive correlation was reported among AS and PS ($r= 0.364$, $p= 0.000$).

Figure 2: Summary of Pearson Correlation (r) between KS, AS, and PS.

DISCUSSION

The pharmaceutical business, university researchers, pharmacy experts, and healthcare providers all acknowledge the new area of Pharmacoeconomics as a health science discipline. The necessity of incorporating Pharmacoeconomics into the process of choosing the best treatment to enhance patient outcomes while keeping costs down was highlighted by the rising expenses of healthcare. Therefore, it is crucial to assess the doctors' understanding and familiarity with the Pharmacoeconomics concept. Evaluating how well cost-effectiveness calculations are integrated into clinical practice is also necessary. The purpose of this cross-sectional study was to gauge the doctors' Pharmacoeconomic knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAP).

Overall, the KAP scores in the present study were moderate, with an average knowledge score of 65.02%, attitude score of 77.34%, and practice score of 71.08%. Limited studies are conducted in Indian medical fraternity to estimate the knowledge and awareness regarding Pharmacoeconomics. A study conducted by Reshma et al. (2020) reported that 70.3% of the participants were aware of the term Pharmacoeconomics.^[4] However, over half of the participants answered less than 75% of the knowledge-based questions on Pharmacoeconomics correctly. The moderate scores suggest that while participants comprehend the significance of Pharmacoeconomics, there remains a need for further education and training to ameliorate their proficiency, particularly in practice.

The results revealed no significant differences in KAP scores between male and female participants, suggesting gender does not play a substantial role in determining awareness or implementation of Pharmacoeconomics. Statistical analysis, though, emphasized significant differences in KAP scores based on qualification and years of experience of the participants. Higher knowledge scores of more-experienced physicians may be attributed to their prolonged involvement in clinical decision-making and increased exposure to the healthcare system that necessitates a better understanding of cost-effectiveness. A study conducted in South India among the postgraduate students of a tertiary care hospital reported that around 28% of the participants were having Pharmacoeconomics-based knowledge.^[9] A lower attitude score among PG participants compared to the UGs may reflect a lack of emphasis the need to bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application and to incorporate the concept of Pharmacoeconomics in PG curriculum. A similar study in Andhra Pradesh reported 55% of the participating PG doctors expressed the need to include Pharmacoeconomics in their PG curriculum.^[9] Another study among the postgraduates claimed that only 24% had a positive understanding of the application of pharmacoeconomic principles; however, only 9% actively incorporate these principles into their daily clinical practice.^[10]

The significant correlation between attitude and practice scores ($r = 0.364$, $p < 0.05$) further highlights the critical role of attitude in influencing clinical decision-making. Healthcare professionals who demonstrated a positive attitude toward Pharmacoeconomics were more likely to incorporate these evaluations into their practice. On the contrary, the weak correlation between knowledge and practice scores indicates that though knowledge is essential, it alone may not be sufficient to This finding can also suggest that practical barriers, such as lack of resources or time constraints, may restrict the implementation of pharmacoeconomic principles in clinical settings, despite having adequate knowledge.^[5,11]

The sample size is one of the study's limitations; it could be increased to increase the findings' generalizability. Furthermore, because study participants may exaggerate or underestimate their level of understanding or experience, self-reported results may add bias. To evaluate how knowledge, attitudes, and practices change over time and in response to specific educational interventions, future longitudinal studies might be helpful.

CONCLUSION

The present study provides valuable insights into the knowledge, attitude, and practice (KAP) of Pharmacoeconomics among physicians in India. The findings suggest that while physicians acknowledge the importance of Pharmacoeconomics in optimizing patient care and cost-effective treatment decisions, their practical application of these principles remains limited. The moderate KAP scores indicate a foundational understanding, but a significant gap persists in translating knowledge into clinical practice.

Notably, the study highlights that gender does not significantly influence Pharmacoeconomics awareness or implementation. However, qualification and years of experience play a crucial role, with senior physicians demonstrating higher knowledge scores due to their prolonged exposure to clinical decision-making. The lower scores among postgraduate students

emphasize the necessity of integrating Pharmacoeconomics into the medical curriculum to bridge the gap between theoretical understanding and real-world application.

A significant correlation between attitude and practice underscores the role of positive perception in influencing clinical decision-making. However, the weak link between knowledge and practice suggests that barriers such as lack of institutional support, time constraints, and limited resources hinder the practical application of Pharmacoeconomics principles. Addressing these challenges through structured training programs, workshops, and policy interventions can enhance the competency of healthcare professionals in cost-effective decision-making.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

All authors have no Conflict of Interest.

FUNDING

None provided.

ETHICAL APPROVAL

As the KAP study involved only the voluntary participation of physicians, focused solely on their perceptions, and maintained complete anonymity and confidentiality of responses, formal ethical approval was waived off.

AVAILABILITY OF DATA & MATERIAL

Data were collected, analyzed and presented in the result section.

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REFERENCES

1. Walley, T., & Haycox, A. (1997). Pharmacoeconomics: Basic concepts and terminology. *British Journal of Clinical Pharmacology*, 43(4), 343–348. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-2125.1997.00574.x>
2. Tonin, F. S., Aznar-Lou, I., Pontinha, V. M., Pontarolo, R., & Fernandez-Llimos, F. (2021). Principles of pharmacoeconomic analysis: The case of pharmacist-led interventions. *Pharmacy Practice (Granada)*, 19(1), 2302. <https://doi.org/10.18549/PharmPract.2021.1.2302>
3. Preetha, V., & Vasundara, K. (2023). A pharmacoeconomic study on cost variation of dyslipidemic drugs available in Indian market. *National Journal of Physiology, Pharmacy and Pharmacology*, 13(3), 454–458.
4. Reshma, R. A. R., Sudha, M. J., & Viveka, S. (2020). Knowledge and practices regarding pharmacoeconomics among resident doctors in a tertiary care teaching hospital. *International Journal of Basic & Clinical Pharmacology*, 9, 1114–1118.
5. Alzarea, A. I., Khan, Y. H., Alanazi, A. S., Butt, M. H., Almalki, Z. S., AlAhmari, A. K., Alshali, S., & Mallhi, T. H. (2022). Barriers and facilitators of pharmacoeconomic studies: A review of evidence from the Middle Eastern countries. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(13), 7862. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19137862>
6. Abdulkader Mohamed, R., Abdul Rahim, N. A., Mohamad, S. M., et al. (2022). Validity and reliability of knowledge, attitude, and practice regarding exercise and exergames experiences questionnaire among high school students. *BMC Public Health*, 22, 1743. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-022-14147-z>
7. Feleke, B. T., Wale, M. Z., & Yirsaw, M. T. (2021). Knowledge, attitude and preventive practice towards COVID-19 and associated factors among outpatient service visitors at Debre Markos comprehensive specialized hospital, North-West Ethiopia, 2020. *PLoS ONE*, 16(7), e0251708. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0251708>
8. Poddar, P., Maheshwari, A., & Shylasree, T. S., et al. (2022). Knowledge, attitudes and practices towards COVID-19: A cross-sectional survey. *Indian Journal of Gynecologic Oncology*, 20, 23. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40944-022-00624-1>
9. Jayasree, D., Uppu, B., & Devi, B. V. (2016). A study on awareness of pharmacoeconomics among

postgraduates in a tertiary care teaching hospital. *International Journal of Research in Medical Sciences*, 4, 1597–1603.

10. Tabassum, R., Hussain, S., & Banday, M. (2016). Evaluation of pharmacoconomics awareness and its application among postgraduates of a tertiary care hospital: A cross-sectional observational study. *Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical and Clinical Research*, 9, 145–147.
11. Alefan, Q., et al. (2021). Barriers to implementing pharmacoconomics: Interview study. *Expert Review of Pharmacoconomics & Outcomes Research*, 21(1), 93–104. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14737167.2020.1766969>